

Evaluation of Two Music Tactile Display Encodings for Cochlear Implant Recipients

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the effect of using haptic feedback in conjunction with music using a tactile display worn as a belt. Studies have shown that Cochlear Implant (CI) users have limited ability to perceive music. This is partly due to the fact that CIs have been developed and optimized for speech and not for delivering the acoustical properties of music. The idea behind this work is to use tactile stimulation to enhance the musical experience of CI recipients. Using a tactile display from a previous project, music was encoded and mapped to the display to allow for more senses to be involved during the listening experience. To test if this had a positive impact, we compared two encodings with music filtered through a cochlear implant simulator and just the filtered music as control. Our results suggest that using tactile feedback can positively affect the experience of listening to music.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cochlear implants have improved speech recognition significantly [1]. However, living with a cochlear implant (CI) also presents a number of obstacles. This paper will discuss the impact CIs can have on the experience of listening to music, and a possible way of improving their listening experience, to increase the users' quality of life. CIs work very well for speech signals in quiet environments and for rhythm perception, but are severely lacking in other features such as timbre and pitch [1]. The focus of the CI processing strategy is often to remove temporal fine-structures and preserve temporal envelopes to improve speech perception. This unfortunately also removes much of the spectral information [2]. Even with further advancement in CI technology, obtaining a new implant is costly and as such, a different approach could be useful. Even though CI users face poor music perception studies have shown that there might not be a relationship between music perception and music enjoyment [1].

This initial study reports on the first steps taken towards the development of a tactile display representation, of music for cochlear implant recipients. It is partly based on previous work in the Sound of Vision project [3–6] where a tactile display in the form of a belt was developed with an array of 60 motors to assist navigation for vision impaired people. Specifically the belt is reused for this initial study. The belt (see fig 2) is reused to save development time and to quickly create an underlying foundation for launching other studies on new mappings, placement of tactors, choice of songs and so on.

Other haptic designs have been made to further the experience for the hearing impaired such as the the emoti-chair [7] and Eagleman's vibratory vest [8] but neither focus on tactile stimulation in conjunction with CIs.

The aim of this study was to gauge if introducing the somatosensory modality through tactors with music, would at all change the enjoyment of listening to music for CI users. Using the tactile display previously mentioned, two different ways of mapping music to the tactile display were developed. A cochlear implant simulator was used to filter music to stand in for actual CI users. The two mappings in conjunction with simulated CI music, were compared to each other and to the experience of just listening to the simulated version of the music. The result show a significant preference for the belt as opposed to just the simulated music by itself.

2. COCHLEAR IMPLANTS

As opposed to normal hearing aids, the cochlear implant is, as the name suggests, an implant. The implant has an electrode array surgically placed into the cochlea (see fig. 1). On the outside, a microphone picks up sound which a processor can then analyse to determine the level of stimulation each electrode is sent [9]. This information is sent via radio transmission. The implant then sends electrical signals to the electrodes placed in the cochlea. The signals activates the auditory nerves which is then projected to hearing related regions of the central nervous system, same as any normal hearing person. Many factors determine what the end experience is for a CI user. The most important one is the amount of channels the CI has. The implant divides the sound into channels which drive the aforementioned electrodes. Because of the size of the cochlea organ,

Figure 1. diagram of the hearing organ with CI [10]

the amount of electrodes and wires you can fit is limited. Since the sound is divided into a limited amount of channels a lot of fidelity is lost, especially in pitch perception. While this technology has enabled people to hear again, it leaves a lot to be desired in the way of music enjoyment.

2.1 CI simulation

It is very hard to determine the exact experience of a CI user. A multitude of factors are involved: The technological features of the implant itself, surgical factors, physiological factors of the user, factors concerning the users hearing impairment: duration, age of onset, auditory training and so on [9]. For accurate simulation; testimonies, indirect observations and analysis of audio signal transformations can be investigated. The Cochlear Implant Simulation(CIS) [9] uses these to approximate the listening experience of a CI user. For this initial study of the influence of haptic stimulation on music experience of CI users, we used this simulator with people with normal hearing, instead of testing actual CI users. There are other, more recent simulations available such as the SPIRAL [11, 12] but it was decided that the CIS was sufficient for this project, especially since it has not been shown whether the SPIRAL provides better music sound quality.

3. THE BELT

The tactile display that is used in this study was designed and built in the H2020 project Sound of Vision (no: 643636). It consists of an array of 60 motors in a 6*10 grid (see fig. 2). It is meant to be worn around your waist with the motors on your belly. It uses parallel rotating ERM motors that are controlled with an arduino microcontroller connected to a computer.

4. MAPPING MUSIC TO AN ARRAY OF TACTORS

The question of what kind of mapping provides the best experience is not an easy one to answer. Designing tactile encoding for good music appreciation is not trivial, as there are number of factors that need to be considered: focus on providing stimulation to differentiate pitches or focus on

Figure 2. Belt consisting of 60 motors

the beat and percussion, focus on low frequencies, mids, highs or the entire spectrum, which type of song do we use, is the beats per minute(BPM) and important factor and what hardware are we dealing with.

CI users can perceive rhythm and transients relatively well compared to pitch. With this in mind, a mapping strategy focused on the beat and percussion would not provide as much new information as a strategy focused on pitch. However, PrevotEAU et al. [1] suggests making music more percussive and/or enhancing the lower frequency content may "enhance music enjoyment for CI users."

The type of music to test is also important. We could choose a song that fits a CI user more, such as a genre with a strong steady beat and a relatively simple melody without many layers. This could come from the electronic genre or perhaps pop music. The other direction is something that would be difficult for a CI user to listen to, such as a genre with a lot of layers and complexity [1, 13]. With a genre that doesn't fit a CI user, the addition of a new modality could have a strong effect on the enjoyment of music, however, in choosing a song that does not fit, the experience as a whole could be so bad even engaging other senses would not help it. Since we are taking our first steps in to the development, we chose to go with the more simple option and start with a song that fits CI users.

A 30 second sample of the chorus of Mika - Grace Kelly was chosen. Its beat and bass line is relatively steady. The vocal track is well known for its high variance in pitch which could help CI users detect the change in pitch.

Since CI users can perceive rhythm well, the BPM is not expected to be an important factor. The biggest influence of our choice here involves the limitations of the technology used for this particular initial study. Our base knowledge is also a limiting factor as some decisions require more information to be taken into account.

The hardware used is also an important factor. The tactors used in this study were simple vibrating motors. They vibrate at a certain frequency which changes with the load you put on them. As such, pressing them against a human body, for example, will change the output frequency. This makes it very hard to control. Given this difficulty the intensity was not a variable we decided to map for any of the encodings.

Figure 3. Graph of a 10 second sample after analysis and dividing the sample into bands of 50 Hz. Every frame a corresponding magnitude for a band is found and can be mapped to the belt.

4.1 Mappings

In order to transform music into data that the belt (see fig 2) can interpret, two strategies must be developed. One to determine the specific data that is sent to the belt, and the second being the encoding itself. For this, custom software was developed. The software is split into two parts; Encodings for the belt programmed from an analysis of the music sample, and the software controlling the belt that then executes the encoding. The software is written in python with an arduino sending signals to the belt itself.

As the belt was designed to provide navigational aid to blind people, and has a 6*10 array of motors tactile display, it is easy to draw inspiration for mappings from a visual standpoint. Since there has been very little research in this particular area, this initial study is also intended to set a reference point for future studies. New mappings, tactors and placements of tactors and so on will be compared to this study. Some of the software is the same for every different mapping; analysis of the music and the execution of the resulting encoding. What changes is the encoding. The analysis part of the code runs through a fast fourier transformed piece of music within a specific range of frequencies. If the magnitude of the signal is higher than a certain threshold, that magnitude is saved in a list. We do this for every frequency band. See fig (4). The software controlling the belt is coded to run through a simple txt file which consists the motors targeted by the encoding, their intensities and finally a symbol that denotes a pause. Intensity was a constant number throughout the mappings with the option for customization left in for future iterations. The algorithm will look through the current motors and intensities and send those signals to the arduino, if there is a symbol for a pause it will pause for 10 milliseconds and then look at the next range of motors and intensities. As an example, see fig (3). The file processed is a ten second long sample of jazz music featuring a double bass.

Figure 4. Flowchart diagram outlining the processing. A music sample is sent through an FFT and divided into frequency bands that are used to encode the mapping. This encoding is then processed and sent to the belt.

Figure 5. When the software detects activity in a certain band it activates according to the intensity. In this case the second highest in the 50-100 Hz range and third highest in the 10-50 Hz range.

4.2 The EQ mapping

The first mapping considered divides the music into six bands from 0 to 300Hz, each band containing 50Hz. Each row of motors consists of a band of frequencies. The top row has the highest frequencies and the bottom one the lowest. Each row is also split up into two halves representing the left and right audio channel. The position on the row represents the magnitude of the frequency detected in that band, with the middle one the highest. The left and right extremes are the lowest (before 0) values. For example; if a frequency in the range of 50-100 was detected, the appropriate motors in the second last row would activate (see fig. 5).

4.3 The line mapping

The second mapping considered discards some complexity in favor of a clearer experience. Every row is divided into bands again, but the entire row activates if there is any activity in the band (see fig 6). Again the bands go from 10-50, 50-100 and so on up to 300.

5. EXPERIMENT

A 30 second sample of Mika - Grace Kelly that was processed through the CI simulator (see section 2.1) was used to test three treatments. One is the sample by itself, the second is the sample with the first encoding method (see section 4.2) and the third is the second encoding method (see 4.3). the UEQ test [14] was used with the goal oriented scales taken out. We focused on three subscales: Attractiveness, Stimulation and Novelty with the most important

Figure 6. When the software detects activity in a certain band it activates according to the intensity. In this case the entire line of motors in the 100-150 Hz band.

Figure 7. Boxplot showing the spread of data between the three conditions in the Attractiveness scale

being Attractiveness. The first and second treatment were randomized for every test subject with an assessment given after each treatment. Eight subjects were tested, 6 male and 2 female with a mean age of 33,25. The answers from the UEQ test were transformed from the original likert scale of 1-7 to a score between -3 to +3 where -3 represents the most negative value and +3 the most positive. An ANOVA test was used to test if there was a significant difference between the groups followed by a post hoc test to determine interaction between the treatments.

5.1 Results

There was a significant difference between the treatments on all three subscales. (see fig. 7,8 and 9)

The post-hoc analysis reveals that there was no significant difference between The EQ mapping and The LINE mapping. ($t(14) = -0,039$, P one-tail = 0,485) There was, however, a significant difference between the No Mapping and the EQ mapping ($t(14) = 6,14$, P one tail = 8,03E-06) and between No Mapping and the LINE mapping ($t(14) = 6,513$, P one tail = 6,86E-06).

6. DISCUSSION

Our results suggest that providing haptic stimulation in conjunction with music played through a cochlear implant simulator improves the musical experience of listeners. This is promising in terms of improving the experiences of CI

Figure 8. Boxplot showing the spread of data between the three conditions in the Stimulation scale scale

Figure 9. Boxplot showing the spread of data between the three conditions in the Novelty scale scale

users. But as the experiment was not performed on actual CI users but rather music presented through a CI simulator song, we can not say for certain if we would get the same results if the participants were CI users. While we can be fairly certain the simulator is a good approximation, the experimental participants were all exposed to it for the first time. A CI user, on the other hand, could be used to it to a certain degree and thus the scores might be more neutral. For these reasons we find this path very promising for further studies.

7. CONCLUSION

The experimental results suggest that there is a difference between the experience of listening to CI simulated music with and without the belt keeping in mind there were eight participants which could be considered low. While the scores for both mappings were not especially high, neither mapping was very low. These results are very promising for future iterations, and we will move onward with focusing on the placement of tactors and the choice of tactors themselves.

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